

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6844658>

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Annotation: *This article talks about English language teaching mechanisms based on interactive teaching methods and technologies. Also, the article analyzes the ways of using innovative technologies and interactive teaching methods in foreign language classes and the opinions about its effectiveness.*

Key words: *innovative technologies, interactive methods, English language, lesson, science, methodology.*

INTRODUCTION

At the video selector meeting chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dedicated to improving the system of teaching foreign languages, it was emphasized that from 2021 foreign language teachers will be required to have national and international certificates. This puts a huge responsibility on the shoulders of foreign language teachers. Now, instead of traditional teaching methods, it is necessary to organize the teaching process based on interactive methods using new ICT. This education is also a requirement of the times, and the teacher has to work even more on himself. While paying attention to new methods of teaching in the article, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the type and effectiveness of these methods.

It should be noted that new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European frameworks (CEFR, IELTS) for foreign language teaching and assessment of foreign language teachers' knowledge and skills. According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. The subject of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and specific concepts and skills are given for each of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In many literatures, today the most popular interactive educational methods "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blist-survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", It is noted that it is "problematic education". According to the information, interactive education strategies include "Brainstorming", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Movie-zina", "Muzyorar", "Rotastia", "Rounded snow" styles. Interactive group work in separating interactive educational strategies from the composition of educational methods that the approach to organization is, in a certain sense, comparable to strategic planning based on In fact, these strategies are more interactive education methods, and there are no other differences between them. Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn Diagram", "T-Table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The main points in such exercises in the separation of interactive graphic organizers it is based on written form in various graphic forms. Actually this is a graph work with organizers is more related to interactive educational methods. Let's analyze some of the new interactive methods below.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

"THOUGHTS ATTACK" METHOD

This method shows the students' activities during the training provide, encourage them to think freely and think alike liberation from inertia, various ideas on a specific topic collecting, as well as at the initial stage of the process of solving creative tasks serves to learn to overcome emerging thoughts. The main principle and condition of the "Thinking attack" method is each training Absolutely no criticism of the opinion expressed by the participant prohibition is to encourage all kinds of jokes and jokes. The purpose of this is the free participation of students in the training process is to provide. It is up to the teacher to use this method in the educational process it depends on pedagogical skills and breadth of thinking. The number of students is 10-15 when using the "Brainstorming" method It is advisable not to exceed one person.

BACK TO BACK? - this game sharpens the student's memory and develops listening skills. We put colorful pictures on the table with the left side, we take two students to the board and ask one of them to choose the pictures, without showing the second student, they sit on two chairs facing each other. The child holding the picture tells what is depicted in it in a riddle method, and the second student writes down the words he heard. The student will be the winner if he writes down what he heard clearly and accurately. This game is also great fun for seniors.

BINGO? — to play this game, you have to prepare a little. But it is very interesting. Make 4x4 bingo cards and write words in each box and distribute to students. The words should not be repeated and the students should mark

them as you read them. The first student to mark all the words on the page is the winner.

CONCLUSION

As we have seen, each of the innovative technologies and interactive methods has its own advantages. All such methods include cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods encourage students to prepare thoroughly for lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

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